

HOW TO LEARN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE?

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Abstract: There are viewpoints about ways and methods of learning the language. Becoming reasonably well informed is vitally important in English

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How do we need to learn the English language? Today, this question is gaining widespread popularity on various websites and social networks, and everyone is putting an effort to answer it as best as they know. There are a wealth of articles: "7 secrets of learning English", "5 rules of learning a foreign language". "I came to the conclusion that there are some secrets: 1. Don't be lazy; 2. Learn in a live environment; 3. Practice constantly. "Research", i.e. learning a new language, should be very intense. Study 5-6 hours a day and go without reading a book for a week, study for 1 hour every day for the first week go ahead. And from next week, increase the duration of the lesson. Study little and often. You should learn with interest and pleasure. These are the simple secrets of learning English and any language in general. Acquiring them is enough to achieve your goal. I think that those who can easily learn a foreign language are not "God gifted", but they are simple people, and they have achieved it only because of conscious or unconscious adherence to principles. If you notice, their outlook and thinking are also different than their peers. Another thing which is worth mentioning is that, one person who knows one language is two people who know two languages. Spending the life given to a person, to pass from the world as "one person" should be regarded as a tragedy, so to speak! The main thing is that, you should enjoy from learning a foreign language. Then you can enjoy this process! Write new words. Keep a notebook and write down new words, phrases and sentences you come across. Memorize those words and watch movies again with subtitles if possible and then without subtitles. Try to apply your written words in practice. First of all, a person has to find out what he likes to do. Maybe you like listening to music, watching movies or shows and talks of famous people? Maybe you like reading, listening to audiobooks, or discussing the news? Make the most of your interests in learning a foreign language! When you start learning a foreign language, close your eyes and imagine for a moment what kind of worlds will open for you. Now you have the right to do everything you like in a new language, new culture, mentality and history. This is very wonderful! The best psychologists and

teachers have understood that, the success of the educational process is interest and pleasure. This is one side of the coin. The second part is to understand the importance of future results for yourself. You can understand English speech fluently and any them. It's fun to dream about the possibilities if you can express your thoughts in English as easily as you speak in your native language! With this, you will rediscover for yourself the culture of not only Great Britain, but also the USA, Canada and other English-speaking countries, as well as the whole world. The second "secret" is to create a comfortable zone. The main method of successfully learning a foreign language is imitation and repetition. Endeavour to learn the language not from books, but from life: listen to audio, watch videos, talk with people around you in the foreign language that you are learning. While learning English, don't limit yourself with lessons, open your heart and mind to the language, it will give you water from the source of meaning. News and movies can also be found in English. The third secret is to practice constantly. Each person has his own characteristics, talents and virtues. He can use it. You don't have to learn a language based on old methods! If you want, create a new methodology for yourself, don't be afraid to break the mold, change certain rules and regulations! Do not torture yourself and force your brain to study for 3-5 hours, learn the language, learn, just learn. You should learn, not because it is necessary, but make it your favorite activity. It's easier to move towards a goal with a hobby... Don't forget to motivate yourself! - Think about how you want to achieve your goal? If you want to learn English in three years, practice one hour a day. If you train for one and a half to two hours, you will reduce the time to reach the goal by half. As a result of two to three hours of training, you will speed up your "development" three to four times! Reading in a foreign language is one of the best ways to learn a language. Determine what you are interested in reading: books, magazines, newspapers, posts and messages on the Internet and social networks ... the main thing is that it is in the language you are learning. What you may not know is that there are strategies to spend most of your time and energy effectively . The first is comprehensible input, which is a great way to be exposed to (hear or read) something in a new language and learn to understand it. Comprehensible output is the second element, and not surprisingly, it means learning to produce (speak or write) something in a new language. The third element is review or feedback, which basically means identifying mistakes and making changes to the answer. These three elements are the building blocks of your language practice, and an effective study plan will maximize all three. The more you listen and read (input), the more you speak

and write (output), the more you go back and learn from your mistakes (review and reflection), your language skills it grows so much. What you may not know is that there are strategies to help you study more effectively to make the most of your time and energy. Design a curriculum that maximizes all three dimensions of language acquisition: comprehension (input), production (output), and error detection and correction (review, feedback). Learning a new language involves listening, speaking, reading, writing, and sometimes even a new alphabet and writing format. If you focus on just one activity, the rest will fall behind. This is actually a common pitfall for language learners. For example, it's easy to focus on reading comprehension while reading, in part because written language is often easier because you have a full textbook first. DO: Focus on balance: practice speaking and writing and make sure you incorporate the three basic principles of input, output, and feedback. we hope that.

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